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THE IMPACT OF DIGITALIZATION ON FINANCIAL OPENNESS IN SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES

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The article clarified the concept of special economic zones (SEZ). The purposes of their creation were defined, the types were shown, as well as the features of the functioning of the SEZ. In modern conditions, there are many different approaches, tools, formats for the creation and evaluation of the functionality of the SEZ, which should be paid attention to. It was noted that

the formation of the SEZ has the following goals: supporting the national strategy of economic transformations; forming growth poles in the economic space of the country; attracting foreign direct investment; solving labor market problems; using as an experiment for changes in socio-economic policy; promoting diversification of the economy, transfer of new technologies. Having studied the experience of creating SEZs, the authors offer their own vision of using the positive Chinese experience. The high interest of Russia and China in developing cooperation in special economic zones and in the joint promotion of digital technologies was substantiated. Using the examples of free economic zones in China, an analysis of the impact of digitalization on their development was carried out. It was noted that the digital economy contributes to the development of Chinese free economic zones in the following areas: promoting financial openness and innovation; facilitating and stimulating trade; changing government functions and reforming the investment management system. The barriers to digitalization of Russian SEZs were identified, which manifest themselves in an insufficient level of digital readiness, a shortage of competent personnel for the digital economy, legal and regulatory barriers, financial constraints, low efficiency of resource allocation in the implementation of information and communication technologies, as well as risks associated with digitalization.

Keywords: special economic zones, financial openness, investment, innovation, digitalization, digital economy.

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